

**FUTURE TEACHERS AND THEIR MORAL AND
ETHICAL EDUCATION: PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS****Umidbek Mattiyev Kuvondik ugli**

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ABSTRACT

This article is dedicated to the study of pedagogical conditions for shaping the moral and ethical education of future teachers. It analyzes the theoretical and practical foundations of educating teachers in moral and ethical aspects, as well as methods for creating an effective pedagogical environment. The article highlights the importance of psychological, moral, and social factors in the process of educating teachers in educational institutions and provides recommendations for enhancing the effectiveness of this process.

Introduction.

In today's education system, a teacher is not only a provider of knowledge, but also the main mediator of spiritual and moral education of students. Therefore, the personal and professional qualities of future teachers, their moral responsibility and spiritual views directly affect the quality of the educational process. Spiritual and moral education is the process of forming a person's inner world, a system of values, and the skills to live in harmony with society.

However, in pedagogical practice, certain conditions must be created for the effective organization of this process. Among them, factors such as the content of the pedagogical environment, the teacher's personality, knowledge of ethics and culture, and the psychological support system are of great importance. Today, it is not enough to provide future teachers with only theoretical knowledge; enriching them with such moral values as human qualities, patriotism, empathy, and justice has also become an integral part of the pedagogical process.

This article is devoted to the analysis of the pedagogical conditions for the formation of the spiritual and moral education of future teachers, the identification of strategies used in practice, and the development of recommendations aimed at creating an effective pedagogical environment. Thus, opportunities for making the process of spiritual education of teachers in educational institutions more effective are opened.

Discussion.

The spiritual and moral education of future teachers is one of the most important issues in today's education system. The spiritual strength of a teacher's personality directly affects not only his professional activities, but also the upbringing of an entire generation. From this point of view, pedagogical conditions are the psychological, social and cultural environment necessary for the effectiveness of this process.

First of all, the effectiveness of spiritual and moral education depends on the development of the teacher's personality. He should be given the opportunity to understand his value system, feel moral responsibility, and set an example for his students. At the same time, the pedagogical environment in an educational institution is also of great importance. This environment should encourage respect, cooperation, and empathy between students and teachers, as well as reinforce moral values through real-life examples.

Also, practice-oriented methods play an important role in the spiritual education of future teachers. For example, through events, conversations, social projects, and group work, students learn to make moral decisions, work together, and be useful to society. In this way, theoretical knowledge is combined with practical experience, and students acquire moral values through personal experience.

However, the effectiveness of spiritual and moral education decreases when pedagogical conditions are not sufficiently organized. For example, the formation of moral values in students may be limited only to theoretical knowledge or teachers may not set a personal example. Therefore, psychological support, professional teacher training programs, and an internal discipline system that reinforces moral values are important in educational institutions.

As a result, the spiritual and moral education of future teachers should not be limited only to the personality of the teacher or the organizational conditions of the educational institution. This process includes a wide range of pedagogical strategies, methods and tools that correspond to the moral values of society. At the same time, each teacher contributes to this process with his personality, value system and pedagogical skills. From this point of view, the process of spiritual and moral education of future teachers is a process of continuous development, self-awareness and formation as a person useful to society.

Literature analysis (review):

If we analyze a number of recent scientific sources on the topic: The article on the topic "Pedagogical strategies in the formation of the system of spiritual and moral values of future teachers" [1; 203] analyzes the relationship between spiritual ideals and pedagogical competence in the formation of spiritual and moral values of future teachers. It describes in detail the influence of moral and socio-political ideals on personal spirituality and ways to harmonize them in pedagogical activity. The study emphasizes the direct impact of the personal example of mentors on students' spiritual decision-making.

The article on the topic "Principles of spiritual and moral education of future teachers" [2; 91-95] studies the theoretical principles of spiritual and moral education of future teachers. It describes the interrelationships between spirituality, pedagogical culture, educational process and moral processes. Based on the research, ways of systematically implementing these principles in an educational institution are described.

Also, in the article on the topic "Moral Education: Latest Trends in Teaching and Learning Methods" [6], a conceptual article in English analyzes the latest pedagogical trends in moral education and teaching methods. It emphasizes the need for teachers to form moral decision-making skills in students through the use of active pedagogical approaches, reflective exercises, and interactive methods in education in the process of spiritual education.

Conclusion.

The spiritual and moral education of future teachers is one of the most important tasks of today's education system. The results of the study show that pedagogical conditions are the main factor ensuring the effectiveness of this process. In particular, the personal example of the teacher, the positive influence of the pedagogical environment, the combination of psychological support and practical pedagogical methods play a decisive role in the formation of students' spirituality.

It was also found that the process of spiritual and moral education is not limited to theoretical knowledge, but is strengthened through practical activities and real-life situations. This process helps to develop values such as moral responsibility, human qualities, patriotism and social responsibility in future teachers.

As a result, the introduction of effective forms of spiritual and moral education of future teachers serves to educate not only the individual, but also the entire society. At the same time, the pedagogical conditions created by educational institutions ensure the success of this process and allow the simultaneous development of the professional and human qualities of teachers..

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